

Original Article

Computational and experimental investigation of thermally auxetic multi-metal lattice structures produced by Laser Powder Bed Fusion

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Abstract

Certain applications require highly accurate relative positioning of components despite large variations in ambient temperature. As a potential solution, additive manufacturing technologies, such as laser powder bed fusion, enable the production of metamaterial structures with complex local geometries that can be designed to achieve the desired thermal and mechanical behaviors. Recent advances enable the processing of multiple materials within a single build to achieve composite structural properties that are infeasible using conventional single materials. This study investigates the potential of tailoring the structural thermal expansion properties of several configurations of a multi-metal re-entrant lattice structure made of stainless steel 316L and the copper alloy CuCr1Zr. Unit cells and lattice structure segments with theoretical coefficients of thermal expansion ranging from $1.64 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ to $2.51 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ (16% more than CuCr1Zr) are evaluated computationally using finite element analysis and validated experimentally using digital image correlation. Imperfections related to the manufacturing process are shown to have a significant effect on net expansion. The results indicate relatively good agreement despite the imperfections. The study demonstrates the feasibility of designing and fabricating metal lattice structures for a specific thermal expansion within, as well as above and below, the range of thermal expansion of the parent materials.

Keywords: laser powder bed fusion, finite element analysis, multi-metal composite, auxetic lattice structure, thermal loading, digital image correlation

1. Introduction

For space-borne applications, components must be lightweight and able to withstand the shock and vibration that occurs during a rocket launch [1,2]. Furthermore, the structures must prevent thermally induced stresses and distortion when exposed to extreme environmental temperature conditions. Therefore, sensitive structural components for space applications are produced of lightweight materials that exhibit low thermal expansion for large variation of temperatures [3,4]. Unfortunately, these materials can be challenging to source and manufacture, and they may be toxic to human health (e.g., Beryllium alloys [5]). Low-expansion Invar 36 has a high density that is suboptimal for this application [6]. Recent advances in additive manufacturing (AM), however, enable the fabrication of lightweight structural components using non-toxic (e.g. magnesium alloy AZ91D) and available materials [7].

These components may consist of so-called thermally auxetic meta-materials (TAMMs), which are characterized by their ability to undergo reversible shape changes

in response to temperature changes. Under thermal loads, the meta-materials exhibit auxetic behavior, i.e., they expand laterally when stretched and shrink when compressed [8,9]. With this capability, they can be designed to exhibit a wide range of expansions, including zero or negative values. This distinctive behavior has attracted considerable research interest due to its potential for creating self-regulating and adaptive structures in fields such as aerospace, robotics and biomedical devices [10]. The advantages arise from superior resistance to indentation, variable permeability, acoustic absorption, impact resistance, vibration damping, synclastic behavior, constant deceleration of an impacting projectile or stable reaction force during loading [11].

Among the known meta-materials with thermal transformation ability, two-dimensional re-entrant honeycomb lattice structure and its variations are the most frequently documented [12]. The structure consists of a basic geometric element with eight struts, so-called the unit cell, with different angles between neighboring struts. By rotating the unit cell about the axes of the coordinate system, the structure can be extended to exhibit thermally auxetic behavior in all three dimensions. Another planar structure frequently mentioned in the literature is the anti-tetrachiral structure, which is capable of a similar transformation [13]. Apart from the individual struts, the structure consists of circular, rotatable elements that help increase the transformation capabilities. However, as geometry becomes more complex, manufacturing problems can arise.

The TAMMs have the potential to achieve effective transformation, especially when multiple materials with different thermal expansion are used in a single composition [14]. In these structures, the thermally auxetic behavior is achieved by the differential expansion or contraction of different materials in response to thermal changes. However, the production of multi-material compositions is associated with processing difficulties that must be solved to allow expansion of their use [15,16].

It was demonstrated by Prajapati et al. [17] who developed a novel concept of multi-material AM based on a hybrid 3D printing and foaming process in which fused filament fabrication (FFF) and foam-filling of closed-cells were performed simultaneously. Controlling foam expansion proved to be challenging and could lead to failure of the build process. Similar experience were made by Kazemi et al. [18], who presented a numerical homogenization method for the design of a lattice structure, where each strut can be made of a different material to optimize the effective properties. However, the authors acknowledged that the designs produced by the proposed method still involve some production challenges, mainly caused by the overlapping of the struts. Yavas et al. [19] drew inspiration from bones with a spongy soft-core and a compact hard-shell to develop multi-material structures with tunable mechanical properties such as stiffness, strength, and energy absorption using multi-material FFF. The energy absorption capacity achieved by varying the ratio of core-to-strut thickness was increased 2-3 times compared to the single material composition. On the other hand, the experimental tests revealed lower flexural strength of the PLA-TPU interfaces due to premature failure at the interface.

Boley et al. [20] considered the production of shape-morphing multi-material lattice structures to be too challenging because the key parameters were difficult to control. To overcome this problem, he developed a new technique for printing elastomer inks to produce so-called heterogeneous 4D lattice structures. A mechanism for controlling the morphing structures was based on multiplexed bilayer ribs composed of materials with different coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs). Unfortunately, the study did not

focus on the comparison between the real function and FEA estimation of the transformation mechanism capabilities. A similar principle of process parameter optimization was applied by Sarvestani et al. [21], who investigated the influence of architectural parameters and material combinations on Poisson's ratio and CTE of polymer lattice structures. His team confirmed computationally that it is possible to achieve positive, near-zero or negative CTE with TAMMs. However, the study lacked comparison with experimental performance. Cukrovic et al. [22] developed a method for automating the design of lattice structures based on the alternate deposition of soft and stiff struts within a 3D multi-material lattice structure with desired deformation. Despite the proven reliability of the numerical simulation environment used, additional analyses through numerical and experimental validation were required to reliably describe the hyperelastic nature of the printed structures.

Subsequent studies have shown that one of the most valuable properties of auxetic lattice structures is their ability to achieve different CTEs depending on the geometric configuration and the parent material [23]. This property can be exploited to create structurally robust designs that exhibit minimal or zero thermal expansion while maintaining high stiffness [24]. This is particularly useful for applications where dimensional stability is critical.

However, to efficiently utilize such a property, a way had to be found to design multi-material lattice structures for the desired expansion. Unlike auxetic lattice structures that are only mechanically loaded, it is not possible to use existing analytical models to design structures that are thermally loaded [25,26]. The combination of thermal expansion of the parent material and secondary induced deformation of the expanding structure makes the problem non-trivial. The procedures that would allow evaluation of the thermal expansion capability of auxetic lattice structures have not yet been established. The lack of design and analysis tools hinders the industrial application of thermally auxetic lattice structures. The studies have shown that multi-material designs of lattice structures can lead to different expansions of the structure when parent materials with different CTEs are used [21]. When this property is combined with the natural auxetic behavior under mechanical loading, a thermally induced auxetic effect can be obtained. The key factor is the application of boundary conditions that cause secondary internal deformation of the structure during its thermal expansion. As the temperature increases, the lattice structure begins to expand. However, the applied boundary conditions limit the displacement of the lattice structure in the intended direction. Due to the auxetic behavior of the lattice structure, it starts to expand/shrink in the perpendicular direction instead. The expansion/shrinkage rate can be regulated by the geometry composition, the parent materials and the multi-material layouts.

In order to efficiently control the behavior of multi-material AM structures, various approaches to their design have been developed [27]. Kazemi et al. [18] presented a numerical homogenization method that proved effective in producing multi-material lattices to maximize the effective bulk and shear moduli and minimize the effective Poisson's ratio. Venugopal et al. [28] focused on the design of a multi-material lattice structure using topology optimization methods. The algorithm he developed combined octant symmetry and supported elimination filters. As a result, a lattice structure was developed that reduced the overall effective coefficient of thermal expansion and thermal conductivity while maintaining high mechanical strength. The authors emphasized that in the future, the algorithm can be designed to automatically generate lattice structures within a component to achieve lightweight design for the specific

loading criteria and material used. Fu et al. [29] presented a new structure with controllable CTE that consisted of a chiral honeycomb structure connected by a series of inclined struts. Although each individual chiral layer exhibited a positive CTE, a negative thermal expansion was achieved through careful design of the geometric parameters and material components. The effects of various design parameters on the thermal expansion behavior were investigated using analytical and numerical approaches. The development of thermally auxetic structures has witnessed a paradigm shift with the incorporation of multiple metallic materials into a single structure [30,31].

Unfortunately, none of the methods presented for multi-metal structures have been experimentally verified, and many of them have not been experimentally validated at all. Despite advances in design and simulation techniques, there is still a fundamental discrepancy between the predicted thermally auxetic behavior and the real-world counterparts. Current design methods do not consider the outcome of multi-metal laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) processes in terms of the precise configuration and thermo-mechanical behavior of the structure as a whole, and the material junctions in particular.

It is therefore necessary to bridge these unknown areas of knowledge so that thermally loaded multi-metal auxetic structures can be used in real-world applications. In this paper, the design of thermally auxetic structures and their fabrication using multi-material L-PBF are analyzed. By examining the response of produced structures to thermal loading, the issues that contribute to the discrepancy between simulation-to-reality gap are analyzed. These include factors such as resolution limits and material gradients at material transitions, as well as discrepancies between boundary conditions in simulation and experiment.

The selected materials were stainless steel 316L (SS 316) and copper alloy CuCr1Zr, which have been demonstrated to have sufficient compatibility with the multi-material L-PBF process, are well-studied and widely adopted, and have interesting thermal properties [32].

The paper is organized as follows:

Section 2 describes the variants of the chosen structure, including the process of their analysis, production and testing. In Section 3, FEA and experimental results are presented, showing the theoretical potential of the selected configurations and highlighting the main differences between single and multi-material layouts, unit cells and lattice structures under free thermal expansion. This section also describes the production of selected configurations using L-PBF technology and explains the dimensional inspection after production. Section 4 discusses the results in detail and draws the conclusions regarding the approach for the design of thermally loaded multi-material auxetic lattice structures.

2. Methods

The goal of this study was to explore the possibility of tailoring the thermal expansion of multi-metal lattice through structural FEA, and to analyze the sim-to-real gaps based on experimental measurements of the response of additively manufactured unit cells of two materials and structures comprised of arrays of such unit cells.

2.1. Lattice Structure Design

Three variants of a 2D re-entrant lattice structure based on an eight-strut unit cell: The group of structures was chosen due to its relative simplicity and versatility of mechanical performance.

1. For the first basic variant, parallelism between the vertical struts was given. The deviation from vertical for the angled struts was denoted by angle θ , which is equal to -45° (see Table 1 (a)) and leads to a possible negative total expansion under mechanical loading [26].

By changing the θ angle to $+45^\circ$, the second geometric configuration was obtained (see Table 1 - Nominal dimensions and schematic of the re-entrant configuration with θ angle (a) -45° ; (b) $+45^\circ$ and (c) 0° .

2. (b)), leading to a potentially positive total expansion.

The third configuration assumed collinearity of the vertical and horizontal struts (see Table 1 - Nominal dimensions and schematic of the re-entrant configuration with θ angle (a) -45° ; (b) $+45^\circ$ and (c) 0° .

3. (c)), which implies a θ angle of 0° and a potential total expansion close to zero.

	θ [°]	-45°	$+45^\circ$	0°
Parametric unit cell dimensions				
Unit cell geometry	w [mm]	16	16	16
	h [mm]	11.3	11.3	8
	l [mm]	11.3	11.3	8
	t [mm]	1	1	1
Lattice structure unit cell geometry	w [mm]	8	8	8
	h [mm]	5.65	5.65	4
	l [mm]	5.65	5.65	4
	t [mm]	0.5	0.5	0.5
		(a)	(b)	(c)

Table 1 - Nominal dimensions and schematic of the re-entrant configuration with θ angle (a) -45° ; (b) $+45^\circ$ and (c) 0° .

For simplicity, only configurations with a ratio of vertical (l) to horizontal (h) strut length of 1 were considered. In addition, the width (w) of all configurations was held constant.

The size of the unit cells and the lattice structures, as well as the number of unit cells in a structure, were determined in a preliminary study using parametric FEA. The number of unit cells in the structures was varied until a stable deformation was achieved in the inner region of the structure. With this approach, the minimum size of the lattice structure was set to either 6x6 unit cells or 7x6 for structures with a horizontal shift of the unit cell rows.

A compromise had to be made between the minimum size of the unit cell and the slenderness of the struts to allow measurable deformation during heating. Therefore, a width of 16 mm was used for a stand-alone unit cell and a width of 8 mm for a unit cell in lattice structure. A strut thickness of at least 0.5 mm was used for all configurations due to the current limitations of multi-metal L-PBF technology. An additional 0.5 mm of material was added to the boundaries of the lattice structure or alone standing unit cell to reinforce the outer hull.

For the design of multi-metal specimens, only configurations with a minimum number of material transitions were considered (Figure 1). Some of the transitions had to be duplicated to allow the formation of a unit cell field that forms a lattice structure. (layouts 5, 6, 7, and 8). The same duplication was applied to unit cells to keep consistent multi-metal compositions for unit cells and lattice structures. In total, two single-material and ten multi-metal configurations were tested for each geometry.

Figure 1 - All geometries considered, from full SS316L to full CuCr1Zr layout (the dashed boxes indicate the configurations that were printed and tested experimentally)

2.2. Finite Element Analysis of Thermal Expansion

Numerical simulations of the effects of thermal loading on unit cells and lattice structures were performed using the static structural module of ANSYS Workbench 22.2 (Ansys Inc., Canonsburg, Pennsylvania, USA). The main objective of the simulations was to estimate the thermal expansion of the meta-material and to

investigate its deformation patterns. Both unit cells and lattice structures were tested in single material configurations and various multi-metal configurations with swapped materials (Figure 1).

2.2.1. Material Parameters

The materials used in this study were SS316L and a copper alloy CuCr1Zr. They were selected based on their demonstrated processability within the multi-metal L-PBF process [32], widespread industrial adoption, and the inequality of their CTEs. The materials were modelled assuming isotropic linear elastic behavior and CTE. The mechanical properties of both materials are listed in Table 2.

Mechanical property	Value		Unit
	SS316L [33]	CuCr1Zr [34]	
Young's modulus E	193	110	GPa
Poisson's ratio ν	0.31	0.34	-
Coefficient of thermal expansion CTE	1.98×10^{-5}	2.17×10^{-5}	$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$

Table 2 - Material properties of SS316L and copper alloy CuCr1Zr.

2.2.2. Model of geometry

A beam element definition was used to create the geometry model (Figure 2). Quadratic three-node beam elements (type BEAM 189) were considered based on their application of Timoshenko beam theory and that they account for shear deformation effects. The model was built using Python API V20 embedded in the Space Claim modeler in ANSYS. A minimum of twelve elements were used to discretize each strut length according to a mesh sensitivity study.

Figure 2 - Graphical representation of BEAM 189 element model.

2.2.3. Initial and boundary conditions

Constraints on specimen motion, representing the clamped fixtures, were applied via displacement constraints in the horizontal and vertical directions of the nodes at the intersections of struts and blue block or red dots (Figure 3). The thermal load was applied as a linear steady-state temperature change that increased uniformly over the entire specimen over a range of 100°C .

Figure 3 - Testing scheme for free expansion of unit cell and lattice structure.

2.3. Manufacturing of Specimens

For each geometric configuration of the unit cell ($\theta = -45^\circ, 0^\circ, +45^\circ$), four specimens were produced and tested: two in single material compositions and two in multi-metal compositions with swapped materials (Figure 1, boxed geometries). Only configurations with $\theta = -45^\circ$ were considered for the structure. Due to the limitations of the powder deposition mechanism, the transitions between the materials were shifted away from the sharp edges at the nodes of the lattices to avoid undue weakening of the structure (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Multi-metal transition locations for (a) $\theta=+45^\circ$ and (b) $\theta=-45^\circ$.

2.3.1. Powder Characteristics

The specimens were produced from SS316L (Carpenter Additive, Widnes, United Kingdom) and CuCr1Zr (Eckart TLS, Bitterfeld-wolfen, Germany) gas atomized metal powder. The chemical composition of both materials is given in Table 3. The particle size distribution was determined with the Bettersizer S3 BT-803 (3P Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Odelzhausen, Germany) using laser diffraction (Figure 5).

SS316L

Elem.	Fe	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Cu	Si	Others
wt.%*	Bal.	18.0	13.0	2.5	2.0	0.75	0.75	≤0.3

CuCr1Zr

Elem.	Cu	Cr	Zr	Others
wt.%**	Bal.	0.5-1.2	0.03-0.3	≤0.2

Table 3 - Chemical composition of Carpenter Additive SS316L and Eckart TLS copper alloy CuCr1Zr powders

Figure 5 - The particle size distribution found by laser diffraction for (a) SS316L, (b) CuCr1Zr.

2.3.2. Machine and Process

All specimens were manufactured using an Aconity Midi+ L-PBF machine (Aconity GmbH, Herzogenrath, Germany). The machine has a cylindrical build volume with a maximum diameter of 250 mm and a height of 250 mm. For single-material builds, the powder was distributed with a standard silicone recoater blade, while for multi-metals, an Aerosint recoater (Aerosint SA, Herstal, Belgium) was used. Two 1070 nm Gaussian-mode fiber lasers (nLIGHT, Vancouver, Washington, USA) were used in parallel mode for material processing. The process parameters used according to Aerosint recommendations are summarized in Table 4.

The specimens were printed lying flat on the build plate, where the 2D lattice geometries were simply extruded in the build direction. The interfaces between the materials were scanned with at least 30 seconds dwell time after the first material was scanned to avoid overheating of these zones. Aside from the contour offset, no other overlaps of laser trajectories were applied for interfaces and no special scan strategy was applied.

Laser Power	SS316L: 150 CuCr1Zr: 485	W
Scan Speed	SS316L: 600 CuCr1Zr: 533.5	mm/s
# Lasers	2 lasers, parallel mode	
Laser spot diameter	80	μm
Layer thickness	40	μm

# Contours	2	-
Scanning strategy	Bidirectional hatching	-
	SS316L: without remelting	
	CuCr1Zr: with 1x remelting	
Interlayer orientation	70	°
Platform heating	No	-
Atmosphere	N ₂	-
Residual oxygen content	<2000	ppm

Table 4 - The L-PBF machine process parameters.

2.3.3. Stress-Relief Heat Treatment

Previous experiments had shown that significant cracking and porosity were likely to occur at the interface of the two materials during the multi-material L-PBF process [32]. In addition, high residual stresses were inherent in the L-PBF process in the as-built state. As such, warping and fracturing of the test specimens was a concern as they were separated from the build plate.

To relieve some of the residual stresses, heat treatment was applied. Heating was performed at a rate of 3 °C/min until 200°C was reached. The specimens were then held for 1 hour. Afterwards, the platform with the specimens was then cooled in the furnace. It should be noted that stresses in the copper alloy were relieved under these treatment conditions, while only minimal stress relief was expected in the stainless steel. However, due to the multi-material nature, it was only possible to subject the entire structure to a uniform heat treatment. After cooling, the specimens were separated from the build plate by electrode discharge machining.

2.4. Dimensional Analysis

Dimensional analysis of the specimens was performed using a Keyence 3D light microscope (VHX-7000, Keyence, Osaka, Japan) at 30x magnification. These measurements provided information on the dimensions of the actual struts and observation of the multi-metal interface. For each structure, measurements were taken on 30 struts from the interior of the specimen using the VHX Measurement Data Tabulation Tool. Separate measurements were made for vertical, horizontal, and inclined struts. The strut thickness was determined as the distance between two parallel lines representing the boundaries of the strut cross-section. The boundaries were found by an automated fitting algorithm based on the color contrast threshold.

2.5. Microstructural Analysis

Sample cross-sections were prepared for metallographic observations following standard grinding and polishing procedures, down to 0.04 µm colloidal silica suspension. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations were conducted with back-scattered electron (BSE) and secondary electron (SE) imaging on a Zeiss EVO10 microscope equipped with an X-max detector (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon-on-Thames, Great Britain) for chemical analyses by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX).

Electron back-scattered diffraction (EBSD) analyses were carried out with a Hitachi SU5000 microscope equipped with EBSD (Symmetry S3, Oxford Instruments) detector. Data were acquired at 20 kV, 21 nA, with a 70° tilt angle and a 3 μm step size. Post-processing was performed with Oxford Instruments' AZtecCrystal software to remove wild spikes and zero solutions (based on 8 neighbors).

2.6. Experimental Measurement of Thermal Expansion

The testing scheme presented in Section 2.2.3. was adopted for the experiment to quantify the thermal expansion capability of the different multi-metal compositions and to compare the results with FEA.

In the test, one end of the specimen fixtures was clamped (Figure 3) such that displacement in the X and Y directions was restricted. Free expansion was assumed for the remaining part of the specimen. In this configuration, the specimen was heated about 100 °C. During heating, the total displacement of the specimen in the vertical and horizontal directions was measured. The vertical expansion was described by the linear coefficient of thermal expansion α_{vert} (CTE α_{vert}), which was defined as the change in length ΔL per original length L_0 with an increase in temperature ΔT (see Eq. 2-1), thus yielding units of strain per degrees Celsius. The analogous method was used to compute α_{horiz} (CTE α_{horiz}).

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta L}{L_0 \Delta T} \quad (2-1)$$

The unit cells and lattice structures were equipped with fixtures on the bottom of the specimens to allow them to be clamped into the machine (Figure 6 (a) and (b)). The displacement caused by the expansion of the clamps and fixtures was compensated for in the measurement.

Figure 6 - Fixtures for clamping of (a) unit cell segments and (b) lattice structures; (c) DIC equipment setup (chamber door open for clarity).

For experimental measurement of their free expansion, the specimens were clamped into an Instron 8801 servo-hydraulic tensile testing machine (Instron, Norwood, Massachusetts, USA, Figure 6 (c)). The system was equipped with an environmental chamber for convective heating (Instron model 3119-607). The temperature was measured by attaching a thermocouple directly to the specimen surface. The two-dimensional displacement was measured using an image-comparative method, digital image correlation (DIC). The method tracked the grey value pattern in close proximity during deformation and compared the changes on individual images [35,36]. A 12 MPx

digital camera from Point Grey (Teledyne Technologies, Wilsonville, Oregon, USA) was used for this purpose. The camera was equipped with a Tokina at-X PRO M 100mm F2.8 D Macro Lens (Tokina, Nakano City, Tokyo, Japan) with a 55 mm polarizing filter.

The camera was located outside the environmental chamber, and the images were taken through the chamber window. Therefore, no thermal influence on the optical measurement system was expected. Calibration images were taken before the initial measurement for recalculating the pixels-to-millimeters scaling and to determine the average measurement error. To avoid background reflections, a thin plate with black anti-reflective foil was placed directly behind the specimen. No matte coating or developer was required for the specimen surfaces since they are rough and provide sufficient contrast for the DIC software to distinguish between specimen and background. The VIC-2D software (Correlated Solutions, Irmo, South Carolina, USA) and the open source software iCorrVision-2D [37] were used for image analysis.

With this setup, images were acquired every 2.5°C while heating from an initial temperature at a rate of roughly $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Linear regression was performed on the strain-temperature data to obtain the CTE of the unit cells and structures.

The CTE of the specimens, calculated from the strain during the experiment, is calculated as the change in the mutual position of the rectangles marked red and blue (vertical and horizontal in Figure 7). For each specimen, the mean values interlaced by linear regression from at least fifteen measurements are calculated. For lattice structures, the measured vertical sections are regularly distributed over the entire width of the specimen to obtain a representative result of the average extent of the specimen.

Figure 7 - Locations of virtual extensometer measurements in vertical (red) and horizontal (blue) direction for (a) unit cells and (b) lattice structures.

3. Results

3.1. Experiments and FEA

The FEA performed using a free expansion setup shows a computed range of CTE values for the proposed geometries in all considered multi-metal configurations at temperature elevated by 100°C . The expansions of the selected configurations are experimentally determined by DIC measurements of specimens (Figure 1, blue

outline). The change in specimen geometry during the heating process is expressed by the total CTE according to Eq. 2-1.

3.1.1. Expansion of unit cells

The results of the beam element model simulations for free expansion of all multi-material geometries, with the exception of vertical expansion of geometry with an angle θ equal to -45° , show the CTE range between the CTEs of the two parent materials (Figure 8, Figure 9, and Figure 10). Specimens made of a single material tend to reach an expansion equal to that of the parent materials, while multi-metal configurations are irregularly distributed within this range. As a result, an antisymmetric layout of CTE around $2.08 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ with overall range of $0.19 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ can be observed.

Both the changes in CTE α_{vert} and CTE α_{horiz} depend on the ratio of the proportions of the materials in the corresponding direction. If the proportion of CuCr1Zr increases in a certain direction, the CTE values increase in this direction until a full copper design and a maximum CTE is reached. The same applies to the vertical and horizontal directions. This property is most evident in the geometry with an angle θ equal to 0° (Figure 8). Due to the 90° angle between neighboring struts, the horizontal struts do not contribute significantly to the expansion of the specimen in the vertical direction when exposed to elevated temperature and vice versa. As a result, several material layouts with the same CTE values can be obtained for this geometry (Figure 8 (b), Figure 9 (b), and Figure 10 (b)).

The -45° geometry is predicted to have a different vertical expansion behavior (Figure 10 (a)) due to the auxetic character of the geometry. The values of CTE α_{vert} for some multi-metal layouts (5, 6, 9, and 10) are significantly lower than in the case of single-material steel layout, while others (3, 4, 7, and 8) are significantly higher than in single-material copper alloy layout. This means that the multi-metal layouts of the geometry with angle θ equal to -45° cover a much wider CTE α_{vert} range than the previous two geometries; almost $0.88 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$.

Figure 8 - Comparison of experiment and FEA for unit cells with $\theta=0^\circ$ geometry when heated by $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for (a) vertical and (b) horizontal expansion.

Figure 9 - Comparison of experiment and FEA for unit cells with $\theta=+45^\circ$ geometry when heated by 100°C for (a) vertical and (b) horizontal expansion.

Figure 10 - Comparison of experiment and FEA for unit cells with $\theta=-45^\circ$ geometry when heated by 100°C for (a) vertical and (b) horizontal expansion.

Based on the DIC measurements, the increase in strain is approximately linear with increasing specimen temperature for most configurations (Figure 11; for raw strain data see Appendix Figure 18). According to the R-squared values, more uniform expansion was observed in the vertical measurement of configurations with an angle θ of $+45^\circ$ and 0° regardless of the material composition. In addition, a more uniform expansion was observed for the SS316L material than for CuCr1Zr, regardless of the measurement direction. Opposite effects were observed for configurations with an angle θ of -45° .

Figure 11 - Measured vertical strain values for unit cells with $\theta=45^\circ$ when heated by 100°C . The strain at the top and bottom center points of the unit cell are used to compute the CTE.

The highest CTE values are calculated at a temperature rise of 100°C using the slope of the linear regression of the strain versus temperature data. The comparison of the results shows that most of the calculated CTE ranges overlap with the values determined by FEA (Figure 8, Figure 9, and Figure 10). Note that the multi-metal configurations of specimens with geometry where angle θ is equal to 0° failed during production and were thus omitted from the experiment.

For some of the specimens, the width of the calculated CTE range exceeds the difference between the CTEs of the parent materials used. This indicates a difficulty that arises when comparing two materials with similar CTE values in complex geometries. For a more in-depth analysis, a more accurate comparison of FEA and average values of the calculated CTEs is required. Such a comparison shows deviations in configurations with an angle θ of $+45^\circ$ and 0° , which are due to a lower expansion of CuCr1Zr, regardless of the measurement direction (Figure 8 and Figure 9). A similar effect is not present in the configuration with an angle θ of -45° (Figure 10). However, the multi-metal configuration with vertically oriented steel struts deviates considerably when measuring the CTE α_{vert} .

3.1.2. Expansion of lattice structures

When the same simulations are performed with lattice structures based on the same geometries, a similar anti-symmetric distribution of CTE values can be observed. With the exception of the vertical expansion of the geometry with an angle θ of -45° , the CTEs of the geometries are in the range of the CTEs of parent materials (Figure 8 vs. Figure 12, Figure 9 vs. Figure 13, and Figure 10(b) vs. Figure 14(b)). Their mean CTE α_{vert} and CTE α_{horiz} values are close to $2.08 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, similar to the unit cells. However, the geometry with an angle θ equal to -45° again exhibits a range of CTE α_{vert} exceeding the range of parent materials (Figure 14 (a)). In this case, the multi-metal layouts of the lattice structure geometry cover a CTE α_{vert} range of almost $0.35 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$.

Figure 12 - Comparison of experiment and FEA for lattice structures with $\theta=0^\circ$ geometry when heated by 100°C for (a) vertical and (b) horizontal expansion.

Figure 13 - Comparison of experiment and FEA for lattice structures with $\theta=+45^\circ$ geometry when heated by 100°C for (a) vertical and (b) horizontal expansion.

Figure 14 - Comparison of experiment and FEA for lattice structures with $\theta=-45^\circ$ geometry when heated by 100°C for (a) vertical and (b) horizontal expansion.

The comparison of the results for configurations with an angle θ of -45° again shows that most of the CTE ranges calculated based on expansion measurement overlap with the values determined by FEA (Figure 14), albeit with substantial variability. Similar to some of the unit cells, the width of the calculated CTE range exceeds the difference between the CTE values of the parent materials used. With similar CTE values of parent materials, the ranges of the measured CTEs may be representative for comparison. A better insight can be gained by comparing mean values and FEA. For almost all specimens, the CTEs are slightly lower than expected, but the trend remains similar to the FEA prediction.

Experimental measurements of the expansion of the lattice structures show mostly consistent values across the virtual extensometers (for raw strain data see Appendix Figure 19), indicating a uniform expansion of the entire structure (see Figure 15). The greatest variability across individual measurements is observed in the stainless-steel specimen with a maximum strain range of $0.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$.

Figure 15 - Structure attached for DIC strain measurement in clamps. White lines indicate the locations of the vertical and horizontal measurements.

3.2. Dimensional Analysis

Microscopic inspection reveals significant differences in the manufactured specimens compared to the original CAD-designed geometries. The deviations differ depending on the parent material, orientation of the struts or machine configuration used (i.e. for single- or multi-metal setup).

The thickness deviations are measured on various struts and then the average values are calculated (Figure 16 (a)). The single-material copper specimens were produced first, which resulted in the large deviations in strut thickness in both the unit cells and the lattice structure (Figure 16 (b)). The root cause was determined to be a misalignment between the two lasers that were used, which was corrected for subsequent builds, as evidenced by the improved dimensional accuracy and precision in the steel and multi-metal unit cells. Even so, the struts tended to be 10-30% thicker than the intended dimensions, with CuCr1Zr struts being thicker than those of SS316L. This can be attributed to the processing parameters and scan paths being sub-optimal.

Figure 16 - Measured thickness of the struts with examples in (a) unit cells; (b) structures (The yellow color in the legend indicates the measured struts).

For the lattice structures, the average results of the dimensional measurements are shown in Figure 16 (b). It can be clearly seen that the struts in the stainless-steel lattice structure are uniform in all orientations, albeit slightly larger than their intended thickness. The single-material CuCr1Zr structure is much thicker than intended due to the laser misalignment issue mentioned in the previous section. Moreover, the average thickness of the struts differs when the production orientation changes. This corresponds to the material used in each strut, where SS316L struts are closer to the targeted thickness than CuCr1Zr struts.

3.3. Microstructural Analysis

Many notable features are observed in the SEM micrograph of the -45° lattice structure in Figure 17 (a). The deposited material has apparently been shifted downward by about 1.2 mm relative to the scanner coordinate system. Whereas the CuCr1Zr was intended only to be deposited in the vertical struts with squared-off ends, it is shifted and extends into the downward-pointing vertex where steel should appear. Lack-of-fusion occurs in these zones due to the application of SS316L parameters, which are insufficient to completely melt the Cu alloy. Horizontal cracks appear in the steel side of the mixing zone of the vertical struts. It is unclear from the image whether these cracks penetrate the full thickness of the structure.

A false-color overlay obtained via EDX has been added to the zoomed images of Figure 17 (b-f) for increased contrast. Of particular interest are the different interface zones, which exhibit different mixing behavior. Figure 17 (e) shows a vertical strut where SS316L has been deposited where only CuCr1Zr should be. As parameters with

a high energy density are used, both materials are brought to a full melt and dragged about as the scan paths naively traverse the displaced interface. This results in a relatively large mixing zone exceeding 2 mm in length. On the other hand, Figure 17 (c) shows a diagonal strut with a relatively short mixing zone of approximately 0.38 mm. This can be attributed to the low energy density parameters, where the copper does not fully melt and is therefore not dragged about by the moving melt pool.

An EBSD phase map (Figure 17 (g)) shows the detected material phases in the mixing zone of a vertical strut, which are primarily FCC-Cu and FCC-Fe. Due to the miscibility gap between Cu and Fe, globules of one material tend to form in the matrix of the other on either side of the mixing zone. High concentrations of Cu are observed on the grain boundaries on the Fe-rich side, which is a precursor to the well-known embrittlement cracking phenomenon observed in Cu-Steel welding [38], which likely explains the cracks visible in Figure 17 (a, c, and d). The inverse pole figure of Figure 17 (h) highlights the grain size of the different materials, where Fe-rich grains are orders of magnitude larger than those of Cu. This can be attributed to the vastly different solidification rates of the two materials, stemming from their difference in thermal conductivity.

Figure 17 - Microscopic images of the as-built -45° lattice structure. (a) SEM image of two unit cells near the corner of the structure, (b-f) EDX overlay indicating regions rich in Cu or Fe at various locations, (g) EBSD image showing the detected material phases in the mixing zone and (h) the corresponding inverse pole figure orientation map indicating the grain boundaries.

4. Discussion

4.1 FEA of unit cells

The FEA of all geometries of unit cells generally shows an increase in CTE with increasing proportion of CuCr1Zr (Figure 8, Figure 9, and Figure 10). In general,

changing the parent material of vertical or horizontal struts from SS316L to CuCr1Zr has a greater effect than changing the diagonal struts. In addition, the parent material for diagonal struts has a similar effect as the angle of inclination.

This observation is consistent when the inclination angle θ changes to 0° (Figure 8). In this geometry, the advantages of the different material layouts of horizontal and vertical struts lose their importance, since the only important role is the extension of the struts in one direction. As a result, the material layouts for this geometric configuration are divided into a group of three specimens with almost the same CTE. At minimum CTE α_{vert} the multi-metal layouts numbers 1, 9, and 5 dominate, at maximum CTE α_{vert} layouts number 8, 4, and 12 dominate (Figure 1 (c)). This indicates that the investigated range of thermal expansion can be achieved by a fraction of the used material layouts.

The same results of CTE α_{vert} are obtained for the observation of a geometry with an angle θ of $+45^\circ$ in the horizontal direction due to the analogous layout (Figure 9 (b)). Slightly different results are obtained for the vertical direction, where milder stepwise changes in CTE α_{horiz} can be observed between the full SS316L and the full CuCr1Zr layout (Figure 9 (a)). This is due to the inclined struts, which contribute to the overall expansion in different proportions.

In contrast, a different situation occurs for a geometry with an angle θ of -45° (see Figure 10 (a)), where the multi-metal layout leads to counterintuitive deviations of CTE α_{vert} due to the auxetic nature of the geometry. This is caused by the interaction of two effects. The heating of the metals generally leads to their expansion, but the orientation of the struts can cause an additional increase or decrease in the distance between their local parts. For this particular geometry, if the expansion of the vertical struts is greater than the expansion of the inclined struts, an increase in CTE α_{vert} can be expected. The maximum is found for layout 5 (CuCr1Zr vertical struts, SS316L elsewhere) at $2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. At the other end of the range, CTE α_{vert} tends to decrease. The minimum value of $1.64 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ is found for layout 8 (SS316L vertical struts, CuCr1Zr elsewhere), which is the inverse of layout 5. This property can be efficiently utilized when a wide range of CTE α_{vert} is required. If the CTE α_{vert} of the parent materials used were more different, it would be possible to design the unit cell for an even smaller CTE α_{vert} value or possibly for a total expansion of zero. This would bring new advantages when designing lattice structures for specific behaviors.

4.2 FEA of lattice structures

The CTE α_{vert} of geometries with an angle θ of 0° and $+45^\circ$ show a similar result to the loading of unit cells. For the geometry with an angle θ of 0° , the CTE increases with increasing proportion of copper alloy in the vertically oriented struts, resulting in the same expansions compared to the unit cells (Figure 8 (a) vs. Figure 12 (a)). At this point, it is important to mention that each geometrical layout has a different expansion mechanism when subjected to a temperature rise. This indicates possible differences in CTE even when the equivalent boundary conditions are applied to unit cells and lattice structures of the same geometry.

It should be emphasized that the geometry with an angle θ of -45° makes it possible to achieve a CTE α_{vert} (Figure 10 (a)) that lies outside the range of CTEs of both parent materials. The highest CTE α_{vert} is around $2.25 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ for material layout number 4 (Figure 1 (a) and Figure 14 (a)), which is similar to the behavior observed for the equivalent layout in unit cell loading, where the results show that CTE α_{vert} reaches

$2.51 \times 10^{-5} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ (Figure 10 (a)). In contrast, the lowest CTE α_{vert} is about $1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ for material layout number 9 (Figure 1 (a) and Figure 14 (a)), which is also similar to the behavior in the equivalent unit cell loading, where the results show that CTE α_{vert} reaches $1.63 \times 10^{-5} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ (Figure 10 (a)). We thus see a slight reduction in the range of achievable vertical CTEs for the structures relative to the unit cells. This is an important feature to consider when designing the size of the lattice structure and its loading conditions for a particular application.

4.3 Comparison of FEA and experiment

Comparison of experimental and computational results of CTE for unit cells yields unexpected results. For geometries with an angle θ equal to 0° and $+45^\circ$, extraordinarily low CTEs are obtained by experimental measurement for material layouts with predominantly CuCr1Zr (Figure 8 and Figure 9). A possible explanation is the dependence of the material's thermal expansion coefficient on its microstructure, which in turn depends on the processing parameters used during manufacture, as described by Yakout et al. [6]. According to the study, the thermal expansion of the material always decreases whenever non-optimal energy is used for powder fusion, resulting in void formation or evaporation of alloying elements. This effect is amplified by a mismatch in material deposition during the production process (Figure 17) where the CuCr1Zr is only partially melted with SS316L parameters.

Another possible reason for reduced expansion is irregular geometric imperfections of the manufacturing process. The differential heating of the struts burdened with imperfections causes the strut nodes to bend laterally instead of moving in the direction of expected expansion. The best example is the CuCr1Zr layout, which achieves the highest CTE α_{vert} deviations, but also contains the largest imperfections. Some amount of geometric imperfections were anticipated due to the layer-wise progression and stochastic nature of the L-PBF process. These factors typically manifest themselves as surface roughness, wherein the profile of the printed body deviates above and below the surfaces of the CAD model. The process parameters and scanner controller tuning and calibration are also common drivers of non-conformities. In addition, the connection in the produced struts is planar and not point-like, as in the FEA. This type of connection restricts the movement of the expanding struts and they are bent more. This effect is stronger in the -45° and 0° configurations due to the mutual position of the struts, so that their total strain is lower.

For the -45° geometry, the FEA and experimental results from the lattice structures and unit cells tend to show a similar trend for CTE α_{vert} (Figure 10 (a) and Figure 14 (a)). However, the different CTE α_{vert} values confirm that the results obtained for the measurement of a single unit cell cannot be arbitrarily transferred to lattice structures of any size. For CTE α_{horiz} , improved agreement between experimentally and computationally achieved results can be observed, except for a specimen with a full SS316L layout (Figure 10 (b) and Figure 14 (b)). According to the model, the changes in CTE are independent of the number of unit cells or their size. However, these parameters can play an important role in experiments, as the influence of imperfections compounds with the increasing size of the structure. In this particular case, it can be seen that the change in CTE α_{horiz} depends much less on the number of unit cells in the horizontal direction than CTE α_{vert} depends on the number of unit cells in the vertical

direction. This also indicates that CTE α_{horiz} is less vulnerable to imperfections that occur during production, as the geometry complexity is lower in this direction.

The gross geometric inconformity observed in this experiment (Figure 16) is likely caused by two factors. One is the coordinate system misalignment between the two scanners, which was identified and corrected during the timeframe when these experiments were conducted. The second is the remelting strategy used for the copper, which may result in the printed geometry being slightly larger than the design intent. Additional parameter development would improve geometric accuracy.

The choice of materials in this study was somewhat arbitrary and almost certainly suboptimal but was chosen as a starting point based on past experience and prior literature. Future studies should evaluate material combinations with larger differences in thermal expansion coefficients and improved multi-material L-PBF processability.

The DIC measurement technique itself may also have contributed to the observed measurement variability. For example, out-of-plane bending or twisting of the structures or unit cells may have affected the measurement. It is also possible that the heating of the structures was non-uniform. This may be improved by adapting the

5. Conclusion

In this work, the tunability of CTE for thermally loaded auxetic re-entrant structure and variations thereof were investigated using FEA and experimental methods. The boundary conditions corresponding to free expansion were applied to compare the thermal expansion capabilities of unit cells and lattice structures made of SS316L, CuCr1Zr, and multi-metal combinations. The computational investigation of the unit cells revealed achievable CTE α_{vert} and CTE α_{horiz} within the range CTEs of used parent materials. The exception was the CTE α_{vert} for the reentrant geometry with an angle θ of -45° , where a minimum of $1.64 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and a maximum of $2.51 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ was achieved. In comparison, the minimum CTE α_{vert} of the lattice structure was $1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and the maximum value was $2.25 \times 10^{-5} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ for the same geometry with the same multi-metal layouts as in the unit cell case. This shows the range of CTE values that can be obtained spans above and below the CTEs of parent materials. The detailed analysis revealed other important conclusions:

- Experimental determination of CTE α_{vert} and CTE α_{horiz} for unit cells showed acceptable agreement with FEA for most material layouts, regardless of the geometrical configuration. The same applies to the CTE α_{horiz} of lattice structures with an angle θ of -45° . The dependence of thermal expansion on microstructure and inaccuracies in the form of strut thickness and geometrical variations played an important role.
- In agreement with computational expectation, the CTE α_{vert} outside the range of CTEs of parent materials was achieved for extreme cases of the unit cell and the lattice structure with an angle θ of -45° . Nevertheless, the CTE α_{horiz} of the multi-material layouts was reduced by an order of magnitude relative to either of the single constituent material lattices.
- Production revealed significant differences between built and CAD-designed strut thicknesses. The extreme case was observed in the CuCr1Zr configuration, where the thickness of one strut orientation was nearly double.

Improvements in multi-material L-PBF processing should alleviate this discrepancy.

- The configurations of the lattice structures achieved the same trend of experimentally measured CTE α_{vert} mean values as unit cells but with lower values. It confirms that the results obtained for the measurement of a single unit cell cannot be arbitrarily transferred to lattice structures of any size.
- For a further assessment of the specific capabilities of various lattice structure designs, different loading case scenarios should be examined. In such a case more precise geometry representation in terms of quadratic elements PLANE 183 should be used. In addition, imperfections in the manufacturing process must be considered.
- In general, customization of CTE for thermally loaded auxetic structures is possible, but the accuracy of the production process has a significant impact on the actual behavior.

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Declaration of interest statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo repository at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11203172>.

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Appendix

$\theta=0^\circ$
SS316L

(a)

(b)

CuCr1Zr

(c)

(d)

$\theta=45^\circ$
SS316L

(e)

(f)

CuCr1Zr

ϵ_y

ϵ_x

(g)

CuCr1Zr (horizontal) + SS316L

ϵ_y

(h)

ϵ_x

(i)

CuCr1Zr (vertical) + SS316L

ϵ_y

(j)

ϵ_x

(k)

$\theta = -45^\circ$
SS316L

ϵ_y

(l)

ϵ_x

CuCr1Zr

CuCr1Zr (horizontal) + SS316L

CuCr1Zr (vertical) + SS316L

Figure 18 - Measured strain of unit cells in vertical and horizontal direction

SS316L

CuCr1Zr

CuCr1Zr (vertical) + SS316L

ϵ_y

ϵ_x

Figure 19 - Measured strain of lattice structure in vertical and horizontal direction.

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